

4onse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

Performance report

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	PP	Restricted to other project participants (including R4D services)	
	RE	Restricted to a group specified by the project (including R4D services)	
	CO	Confidential, only for project and the R4D services	
Status	completed		

Change log

Version ¹	Date	Amended by	Changes
0.1	30-11-2018	D. Strigaro	Create document and prepared manuscript
1.0	30-11-2019	D. Strigaro	Update content with articles published in International Journal of Geo-information MDPI

Partners involved in the work execution

Versions	Partner Name	People involved
0.1	SUPSI	D. Strigaro, M. Cannata
1.0	SUPSI	D. Strigaro, M. Cannata

NOTES:

For comments / suggestions / contributions to this document, contact the Coordinator of 4onse project at massimiliano.cannata@supsi.ch

For more information on the project 4onse, link to <http://www.4onse.ch>

¹ Please start with version number 0.1. Any further minor review will increase the version number by 0.1 while a major review will increase the version by 1.0.

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Executive summary

The data management system used into the 4onse project has been tested under high load scenarios.

The results of this activity were published into the International Journal of Geo-information journal of the MDPI with and Impact Factor (IF) of 1.840 (2018). The publication is open access and available on-line [1] or in attached annex (A01).

Reference

[1] Cannata, M., Antonovic, M., Strigaro, D., & Cardoso, M. (2019). Performance Testing of istSOS Under High Load Scenarios. ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information, 8(11), 467.